

Review

Catgut Acupuncture for Weight Loss: A Review of Clinical Methodologies.

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Abstract

Background: Obesity is a major global health challenge, with its prevalence increasing by more than 50% worldwide between 2000 and 2016. Conventional treatments such as diet, exercise, and surgery often have limitations, including low long-term adherence and associated risks. Within Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), obesity is considered a metabolic imbalance linked to a deficiency of the Spleen and stagnation of Qi and Blood. Catgut acupuncture is a minimally invasive technique that involves implanting absorbable sutures into acupoints to provide continuous, long-lasting stimulation. It has gained attention as a potential adjunctive therapy for weight management, with studies suggesting it works by modulating appetite-related hormones, improving insulin sensitivity, and regulating lipid metabolism.

Objectives: This review aims to summarise the diverse clinical methodologies used in catgut acupuncture for weight loss and to highlight the most commonly used acupoints and their potential mechanisms of action.

Methods: This paper builds on a prior preliminary systematic review by the authors. It analyses the clinical methodologies of catgut acupuncture used in a selection of randomised controlled trials (RCTs). The review focuses on identifying commonalities in acupoint selection, treatment frequency, and duration across the included studies. The most frequently used acupoints are discussed, along with their proposed physiological mechanisms for promoting weight loss.

Results: The analysis of ten studies revealed a wide range of treatment methods, with durations from 6 to 16 weeks and frequencies from once every week to a single implantation for the entire trial. A total of 27 different acupoints were identified, with five points being used most frequently: Tianshu (ST25), Zhongwan (CV12), Zusanli (ST36), Fenglong (ST40), and Shuifen (CV9). The combination of ST25 and CV12 was notably used in seven studies. Mechanistically, stimulating ST25 is thought to influence gastrointestinal function, enteric nervous system activity, and anti-inflammatory responses. CV12 stimulation has been shown to regulate gastric motility, influence the vagus nerve, and modulate hormones such as leptin and ghrelin.

Conclusions: Catgut acupuncture shows potential as an effective adjunctive therapy for weight loss, as evidenced by its consistent ability to improve weight-related outcomes across various studies. The combination of ST25 and CV12 appears to be a core component of the treatment protocol for weight loss. However, further large-scale, well-designed RCTs with long-term follow-up are necessary to confirm the durability of its effects and to establish best-practice guidelines for clinical integration.

Keywords: Obesity; Weight Loss; Acupuncture Catgut; Acupuncture Embedding, Complementary Therapies; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

Citation: Paixão P., dos Santos N.F., Santoro A., Gomes B.F., Caneiras R., Torres R.C., Serra E.M. Catgut Acupuncture for Weight Loss: A Review of Clinical Methodologies. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(3) 10.5281/zenodo.16890171

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 6 August 2025

Reviewed: 12 August 2025

Revised: 14 August 2025

Accepted: 16 August 2025

Published: 17 August 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

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1. Background

1.1. Overweight and obesity

In general, obesity is defined as the excessive accumulation or abnormal distribution of body fat that adversely affects health¹. It is most commonly classified using the body mass index (BMI), although this criterion can be limited and, in some cases, subjective².

Obesity has emerged as one of the most pressing global health challenges of the 21st century, earning the designation of a “21st-century epidemic”³⁻⁵. Its prevalence has increased by more than 50% worldwide, rising from 8.7% in 2000 to 13.1% in 2016⁶. This surge is closely linked to the growing adoption of sedentary lifestyles⁷. In modern societies, daily routines increasingly involve minimal physical activity and greater consumption of high-calorie foods and alcohol, creating a perfect storm for impaired metabolic health^{8,9}. These lifestyle changes slow metabolic rate and significantly increase the risk of overweight, obesity, type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome⁹⁻¹¹.

The burden is particularly evident in industrialised countries, where obesity rates continue to climb at an alarming pace, suggesting a sustained upward trend and an increasing demand for clinical interventions, including bariatric surgery¹². Yet, this is far from being a problem confined to developed nations. Many developing countries are experiencing similar growth in overweight and obesity prevalence, making it a truly global epidemic^{3-5,13,14}.

Beyond its prevalence, obesity is now recognised as a major contributor to premature mortality. In 2019 alone, obesity-related diseases such as ischemic heart disease and stroke claimed approximately 15 million lives worldwide¹⁵. This sobering statistic underscores the urgent need for effective prevention and treatment strategies capable of addressing this escalating public health crisis.

Conventional interventions, including dietary modification, structured exercise, pharmacotherapy, and bariatric surgery, are frequently employed. However, each presents inherent limitations. Dietary and exercise programs often suffer from low long-term adherence, pharmacological agents may carry adverse effect profiles and cost burdens, and bariatric surgery, though effective, is invasive and associated with perioperative risks¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Given the magnitude of this global health challenge, there is an urgent need for effective interventions to promote intentional weight loss. Addressing this requires the development and implementation of affordable, accessible, and evidence-based prevention and management strategies at both the clinical and community levels¹⁹. In this context, complementary and integrative approaches are attracting interest for their potential to support weight reduction through sustained physiological modulation, minimal invasiveness, and relatively low cost compared to conventional medical or surgical options²⁰⁻²².

1.2. Traditional Chinese Medicine

Traditional Chinese Medicine's view on obesity

The Eastern perspective on metabolic disorders adopts a holistic approach, emphasising prevention, the maintenance of energy equilibrium, and the harmonious interaction between the body and mind as essential components^{20,23,24}.

Within Traditional Chinese Medicine, health is fundamentally linked to the balance of the vital energy called “*Qi*.” Metabolic diseases are understood to result from disruptions in the body’s energetic balance, which not only affect the flow of *Qi* but also impact the functioning of internal organs^{25,26}.

This system is grounded in the belief that *Qi* circulates through specific pathways known as meridians or energy channels^{27,28}. Impaired circulation or a deficiency in *Qi* may contribute to the development of various health conditions^{25,27}. The Spleen-Pancreas (*Pi*) and Liver (*Gan*) are particularly implicated in metabolic illnesses, as they play key roles in nutrient metabolism and energy distribution. The Spleen-Pancreas transforms nutrients from food into *Qi* and Blood (*Xue*) and transports them throughout the body. When

its function is deficient, symptoms such as poor digestion, persistent fatigue, and dampness accumulation may arise. The Liver's role involves ensuring the smooth flow of *Qi* and Blood, and its dysfunction (whether through stagnation or deficiency) can manifest as insulin resistance, hormonal disturbances, and chronic inflammation²⁰.

In the case of obesity, Traditional Chinese Medicine views it as a metabolic imbalance where the body's capacity to process and convert food is compromised, leading to the buildup of pathological factors like dampness and phlegm. This condition is linked to a disruption in the Earth element, resulting in Spleen deficiency that promotes dampness/phlegm accumulation alongside *Qi* and Blood stagnation^{29,30}. Emotional influences, including persistent worrying and feelings of frustration or anger, are thought to weaken the Spleen and contribute to Liver *Qi* stagnation, respectively^{20,23}.

For centuries, Traditional Chinese Medicine has been employed in managing various illnesses, with a significant role in obesity treatment^{30,31}.

2. Catgut acupuncture

Acupuncture, a fundamental practice within Traditional Chinese Medicine, is increasingly recognised worldwide as a non-pharmacological therapeutic option embraced by both patients and healthcare practitioners³². Although its origins trace back thousands of years in China, acupuncture began gaining popularity in Western countries from the 16th century onward³³. This therapy consists of inserting fine needles into designated points on the body, called acupoints, guided by the Traditional Chinese Medicine concept of meridians (as mentioned before in this paper)³⁴⁻³⁶.

Over time, various modern adaptations of traditional acupuncture have emerged, including herbal acupuncture, electroacupuncture, laser acupuncture, and catgut acupuncture^{28,37,38}.

Catgut acupuncture, also referred to as acupoint catgut embedding or thread-embedding acupuncture, is a minimally invasive acupuncture technique in which sterile, absorbable sutures such as catgut or polyglycolic acid threads are implanted into predetermined acupoints to provide continuous stimulation over an extended period, typically lasting from several days to weeks. This sustained stimulation is proposed to enhance therapeutic effects compared to conventional acupuncture by maintaining prolonged activation of meridians and associated physiological pathways³⁹.

In recent years, Catgut acupuncture has gained increasing attention as an adjunctive therapy for weight management and obesity. Recent studies indicate that catgut acupuncture may have therapeutic applications across a broad range of conditions, including menopause-related symptoms, depression, obesity, and both acute and chronic pain^{32,40,41}.

Clinical and preclinical evidence suggests that catgut acupuncture may exert weight-reducing effects through multiple mechanisms, including modulation of appetite-related hormones such as leptin and adiponectin, improvement of insulin sensitivity, regulation of lipid metabolism, and potential influences on hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis activity⁴². These multifaceted actions, coupled with its minimally invasive nature and potential for sustained therapeutic impact, have positioned catgut acupuncture as a promising complementary modality in integrated obesity management strategies.

2.1. Clinical evidence of Catgut acupuncture for weight loss

Several human trials and systematic reviews have provided evidence supporting the efficacy of catgut acupuncture in promoting weight loss. In a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial involving 90 obese women with a BMI ≥ 27 kg/m², participants receiving catgut acupuncture demonstrated significantly greater reductions in body weight (-1.65 kg versus -0.38 kg) and waist circumference (-4.84 cm versus -1.68 cm) after six weeks compared to a sham embedding group. This study also reported beneficial hormonal changes, including a decreased leptin-to-adiponectin ratio, without serious adverse effects¹⁶.

Longitudinal observational data from a cohort of 820 patients representing various obesity types further support these findings. Catgut implantation over periods ranging from 90 days up to one year resulted in significant decreases in body weight, BMI, waist and hip circumferences, and body fat percentage, along with improvements in metabolic markers such as insulin sensitivity ($P < 0.01$)³⁹.

Complementing these trials, multiple meta-analyses have consolidated evidence across randomised controlled trials. One meta-analysis of 13 RCTs including 966 patients found that catgut acupuncture significantly reduced body weight and waist circumference compared to sham or no treatment, with additional decreases in hip circumference⁴². Another meta-analysis encompassing 20 RCTs (1,616 patients) demonstrated that acupuncture combined with catgut acupuncture produced superior improvements in BMI, body weight, waist-to-hip ratios, and overall treatment effectiveness compared to acupuncture alone, highlighting enhanced long-term outcomes and patient compliance⁴³.

A network meta-analysis analysing 35 studies involving approximately 3,040 patients reported that combined therapies such as catgut acupuncture with moxibustion, traditional Chinese medicine, or cupping yielded the highest effectiveness in reducing total body weight and BMI⁴⁴. Additionally, a broader review of 73 RCTs (5,872 participants) concluded that catgut acupuncture showed greater efficacy than manual or electroacupuncture methods⁴⁵.

Together, these findings suggest that catgut acupuncture may serve as a valuable adjunctive therapy in integrated weight management programs.

3. Clinical methodologies of Catgut acupuncture for weight loss

This paper builds upon recent research conducted by the authors' group⁴⁶, with a specific focus on the catgut acupuncture methodologies utilised in the RCTs included in that previous study. Table 1 summarises the clinical methodologies of catgut acupuncture, which are analysed further in this paper.

Table 1. Summary of the methodologies applied in the included studies of dos Reis et al.⁴⁶.

Study	Population	Acupuncture points	Additional treatments	Treatment frequency and duration
Jin et al. ⁴⁷	Women going through perimenopause who have central obesity	Zhongwan (CV11), Xiawan (CV10), Shuifen (CV9), Zhongji (CV3), Daheng (SP15), Tianshu (ST25), Guilai (ST29)	Dietary intervention	Catgut acupuncture treatment was carried out every 2 weeks for 8 weeks.
Xinghe et al. ⁴⁸	Overweight adults	Pishu (BL20), Weishu (BL21), Dachangshu (BL25), Zhongwan (CV12), Tianshu (ST25) and Zhangmen (LR13)	None	Catgut acupuncture treatment was carried out every 2 weeks for a total of 12 weeks.
Chen et al. ¹⁶	Obese Women	Qihai (CV6), Shuifen (CV9), bilateral Shuidao (ST28), bilateral Siman (KD14), and bilateral Zusanli (ST36)	None	Catgut acupuncture treatment was carried out every week for a total of 6 weeks.
Garcia-Vivas et al. ⁴⁹	Overweight/obese women	Qihai (CV6), Zhongwan (CV12), and bilateral Tianshu (ST25), Zusanli (ST36), and Sanyinjiao (SP6)	BL20 (Pishu) and BL23 (Shenshu) for moxibustion stimulation.	Catgut was implanted every 3 weeks for a total of 6 weeks. Moxibustion was applied twice a week.
Yang et al. ⁵⁰	Obese adults	Mandatory points - Zusanli (ST36), Fenglong (ST40), Zhongwan (CV12), Tianshu (ST25), and Guanyuan (CV4) Customized:		Catgut acupuncture treatment was carried out every 2 weeks for a total of 12 weeks.

		Central obesity - <i>Daheng</i> (SP15) and <i>Daimai</i> (GB26); Peripheral obesity - <i>Biguan</i> (ST31) and <i>Futu</i> (ST32). Bilaterally.		
Notonegoro <i>et al.</i> ⁵¹	Obese patients	<i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12), <i>Shuifen</i> (CV9), <i>Qihai</i> (CV6), <i>Guanyuan</i> (CV4), and bilateral <i>Tianshu</i> (ST25), <i>Daheng</i> (SP15), and <i>Fenglong</i> (ST40).	Dietary intervention	Catgut acupuncture treatment (implantation) was made once, remaining for the entire 4-week trial.
Chen <i>et al.</i> ⁵²	Obese patients	Two sets were used alternately: First set - bilateral <i>Zhiguo</i> (TE6), bilateral <i>Tianshu</i> (ST25), bilateral <i>Weishu</i> (BL21), bilateral <i>Zusanli</i> (ST36), and <i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12). Second set - <i>Shuifen</i> (CV9), and bilateral <i>Quchi</i> (LI11), <i>Huaroumen</i> (ST24), <i>Pishu</i> (BL20), and <i>Fenglong</i> (ST40).	Diet and exercise education	Catgut acupuncture treatment was carried out every 2 weeks for 16 weeks.
Dai <i>et al.</i> ⁵³	Obese adults	<i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12), <i>Tianshu</i> (ST25), <i>Fenglong</i> (ST40), and <i>Pishu</i> (BL20).	Diet and exercise orientations	Catgut acupuncture treatment was made once every 10 days, eight times in total.
Qin <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁴	Obese Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) patients with infertility	<i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12), <i>Shenshu</i> (BL23), <i>Zhongji</i> (CV3), <i>Guanyuan</i> (CV4), <i>Xuehai</i> (SP10), <i>Sanyinjiao</i> (SP6), <i>Fenglong</i> (ST40), and <i>Zusanli</i> (ST36).	Decoction for nourishing the kidney and promoting blood circulation + Clomiphene and HMG, and Duphas-ton or conventional drugs only.	Catgut acupuncture treatment was made once every 7-10 days, for 12 weeks.
Garcia-Vivas <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁵	Obese women without metabolic syndrome	<i>Qihai</i> (CV6), <i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12), and bilateral <i>Tianshu</i> (ST25), <i>Zusanli</i> (ST36), and <i>Sanyinjiao</i> (SP6)	BL20 (<i>Pishu</i>) and BL23 (<i>Shenshu</i>) for moxibustion stimulation.	Catgut was implanted every 3 weeks for a total of 6 weeks. Moxibustion was applied twice a week.

The included studies employed varying treatment schedules for catgut acupuncture. In some protocols, sessions were administered once every two weeks over periods ranging from 8 to 16 weeks^{47,48,50,52}, while another implemented treatment weekly for 6 weeks¹⁶. Certain regimens applied catgut implantation once every three weeks for a 6-week duration^{49,55}, or once every 10 days for a total of 80 days⁵³. In one trial⁵¹, implantation was performed only once, with the embedded catgut remaining in situ throughout the entire 4-week intervention period. Another approach involved treatments every 7–10 days over a 12-week course⁵⁴. In some cases, moxibustion was incorporated as a complementary therapy, applied twice weekly alongside catgut acupuncture^{49,55}.

Of the ten studies analysed, a total of 27 distinct acupuncture points were identified. Among these, the analysis revealed a clear tendency toward the use of five predominant points in treatment (Table 2).

Table 2. Most used acupuncture points in the analysed RCTs.

Rank	Acupuncture point	Studies
1	<i>Tianshu</i> (ST25)	47-53,55
1	<i>Zhongwan</i> (CV12)	48-55
2	<i>Zusanli</i> (ST36)	16,49,50,52,54,55
2	<i>Fenglong</i> (ST40)	50-54
3	<i>Shuifen</i> (CV9)	16,47,51,52

Amongst these acupuncture points, several combinations can be observed. The combination of the 5 points (ST25 + CV12 + ST36 + ST40 + CV9) was used in one study ⁵².

Three other combinations were observed twice each:

- ST25 + CV12 + ST40 + CV9 ^{51,52};
- ST25 + CV12 + ST36 + ST40 ^{50,52};
- and ST36 + CV9 ^{16,52}.

Furthermore, two combinations were observed 3 times:

- ST25 + CV9 ^{47,51,52}
- and CV12 + ST36 + ST40 ^{50,52,54}.

Finally, two combinations were observed in 4 studies, and one combination of acupuncture points was used remarkably in 7 studies. These are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The most observed acupuncture point combination found in the analysed studies.

Combinations	Studies
ST25 + CV12 + ST36	49,50,52,55
ST25 + CV12 + ST40	50-53
ST25 + CV12	48-53,55

The studies highlight the importance of both ST25 and CV12, used in combination, for the treatment of obesity.

Indeed, the stimulation of ST25 (Figure 1) modulates gastrointestinal function and enteric nervous system activity ⁵⁶, an effect that can plausibly influence energy balance and body weight. Animal studies show that electroacupuncture at ST25 alters markers of enteric neurons and can reduce inhibitory neural signals (for example, decreasing nNOS expression), leading to changes in colonic motility and transit time. By normalising bowel transit and improving gut motility, ST25 stimulation may affect nutrient handling and the timing of satiety signals, which are central to appetite regulation and energy intake ⁵⁶.

Figure 1. Stomach 25 (ST25) according to the World Health Organization ⁵⁷.

ST25 also engages autonomic reflex pathways, including somato-sympathetic reflexes mediated by sensory receptors such as TRPV1, which can alter sympathetic/parasympathetic balance to the gut ⁵⁸. Changes in autonomic outflow influence gastric and intestinal motility, secretion, and blood flow, and by extension can modify gut-brain signalling involved in hunger, satiety, and metabolic rate. Through these neurogenic routes, ST25 stimulation may contribute to reduced caloric intake or improved postprandial metabolism ⁵⁸.

Moreover, inflammation and immune signalling may be additional mechanistic bridges between ST25 and metabolic health. High-intensity stimulation at ST25 has been shown to trigger anti-inflammatory responses via sympathetic pathways and to modulate local cytokine profiles at the acupoint (for instance, decreasing pro-inflammatory mediators and increasing IL-10 in local tissues) ⁵⁹. Because low-grade systemic inflammation is a recognised contributor to insulin resistance and adipose tissue dysfunction ^{60,61}, down-regulating inflammatory pathways via ST25 could improve insulin sensitivity and lipid metabolism, mechanisms relevant to weight reduction and metabolic syndrome.

Furthermore, sensitisation and stimulus-intensity effects at ST25 may be important modifiers of physiological outcomes. Experimental sensitisation of the acupoint (for example, after local irritation) produces a stronger inhibitory effect on intestinal contractions and reveals a dose-response relationship with stimulus intensity ⁶². This suggests that treatment parameters (technique, depth of needling, stimulation intensity, frequency) can materially change the downstream autonomic and enteric effects and, therefore, influence how reliably ST25 stimulation might affect weight-related physiology.

Finally, clinical studies of catgut embedding and broader acupuncture protocols for obesity report changes in metabolic biomarkers, including leptin/adiponectin ratios and improvements in insulin sensitivity ⁴⁶, which are consistent with the neurohumoral and anti-inflammatory pathways modulated by ST25 ^{63,64}. While most clinical trials examine multi-point protocols (so ST25 is rarely an isolated intervention in humans), the mechanistic data for ST25 provide a biologically plausible route by which its inclusion in weight-loss protocols could contribute to reduced appetite, improved glycaemic control, and favourable body-composition changes.

CV12 is traditionally recognised as the Front-*Mu* point of the Stomach and the influential point of the Fu organs (Figure 2). In the context of weight loss and metabolic regulation, CV12 may exert its effects through multiple, interconnected pathways involving gastrointestinal function, neuroendocrine modulation, and inflammatory response regulation.

Figure 2. Conception vessel 12 (CV12) according to the World Health Organization ⁵⁷.

Stimulation of CV12 has been shown to regulate gastric motility and secretion, improving digestion and nutrient absorption while preventing gastric hyperactivity that may contribute to excessive caloric intake ^{65,66}. As well, experimental studies suggest that CV12 acupuncture influences the vagus nerve, thereby modulating gastric emptying and satiety signals transmitted to the brain ^{65,67}. This gut–brain axis regulation can help control appetite and reduce overeating, key factors in weight management.

From a metabolic perspective, CV12 stimulation has been linked to modulation of blood glucose levels and improvement of insulin sensitivity ⁶⁸. These effects may be mediated partly through the regulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis and the modulation of leptin and ghrelin secretion, hormones crucial for energy balance and appetite control ^{69,70}. By restoring hormonal homeostasis, CV12 may contribute to reduced fat accumulation and improved metabolic efficiency.

Additionally, CV12 has demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties by downregulating pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 ⁷¹. As discussed before, chronic low-grade inflammation is a hallmark of obesity and metabolic syndrome, and reducing systemic inflammation may improve insulin signalling and lipid metabolism.

Taken together, the evidence suggests that CV12's influence on gastric motility, gut–brain signalling, hormonal regulation, and inflammation forms a synergistic mechanism for promoting weight loss and metabolic health. This substantiates the role of CV12 as a key point in acupuncture protocols targeting obesity and related metabolic disorders.

4. Final Remarks

Clinical evidence suggests that catgut acupuncture may serve as a valuable therapeutic tool for weight loss and the management of obesity.

Nevertheless, the quality of evidence remains variable, with many studies featuring small sample sizes or heterogeneous designs ⁴⁵. Moreover, despite some studies employing considerable follow-up periods, more research using long-term follow-up is needed to assess whether catgut acupuncture's weight-loss effects are durable or prone to rebound ^{43,46}.

In addition, standardisation of treatment protocols, including acupoint selection, implantation frequency, and duration, is needed to optimise clinical outcomes and improve

comparability across trials. Future well-designed randomised controlled trials with larger cohorts and rigorous methodological frameworks will be critical to confirm efficacy, elucidate mechanisms of action, and establish best practice guidelines for integrating catgut acupuncture into comprehensive obesity management programs.

5. Conclusions

This review highlights diverse clinical methodologies employed in catgut acupuncture for weight loss, revealing commonalities in acupuncture point selection, particularly the frequent use of ST25, CV12, ST36, ST40, and CV9, and variations in treatment frequency and duration.

The combination of these points, especially ST25 and CV12, may represent the core protocol of catgut acupuncture for weight loss.

Despite the observed methodological differences across studies, catgut acupuncture consistently shows potential in improving weight-related outcomes. Future research should aim to standardise treatment protocols to optimise efficacy and reproducibility, while incorporating extended follow-up periods to assess the long-term benefits and durability of treatment effects.

Credit author statement: Conceptualization, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Methodology, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Validation, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Formal analysis, P.P, N.F.S., A.S., B.F.G. and R.C.; Investigation, P.P, N.F.S., A.S., B.F.G. and R.C.; Resources, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Writing - Original Draft, P.P, N.F.S., A.S., B.F.G. and R.C.; Writing - Review & Editing, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Visualization, E.M.S. and R.C.T.; Project administration, P.P, N.F.S., A.S., B.F.G. and R.C. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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